

MATHEMATICAL GAMES IN REDUCING ANXIETY AND INCREASING MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS: BASIS FOR A COURSE PLAN

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ABSTRACT

Mathematics, a fundamental subject essential for logical reasoning and problem-solving across various fields, remains challenging for many students due to its abstract nature and the prevalence of mathematics anxiety, which often hinders their understanding and engagement. This paper aimed to determine the effectiveness of using mathematical games in reducing anxiety and increasing students' mathematics performance. Using a pretest and posttest design, the study was conducted among forty Bachelor of Science in Information Technology students through purposive random sampling. The students were divided into two groups, specifically the control group and experimental group. The control group was taught using conventional teaching strategy, while the experimental group was taught using various mathematical games. A pretest was administered before the intervention to assess the initial level of anxiety and performance in mathematics, which lasted six weeks with sessions of three hours each and followed by a posttest. The findings revealed that there is a statistically significant difference between the mathematics anxiety and performance of the control group and experimental group. This implies that the experimental group had a lower mathematics anxiety level and higher performance in mathematics compared to the control group after the intervention. Thus, incorporating mathematical games could effectively reduce mathematics anxiety and improve students' performance. The results of this study were used as the basis for a course plan in mathematics education.

Keywords: *Mathematics anxiety, Mathematics performance, Mathematical games, Conventional teaching strategy, Mathematics education*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is integral to the school curriculum worldwide. It is considered the foundation of logical reasoning and problem-solving. This subject has an important role in different areas, including computer science and education. The difficulty stems from the subject's logical structure and the use of abstract concepts to represent real-world phenomena.

Mathematics encourages students to acquire knowledge and comprehension of concepts in mathematics to build strong reasoning and decision-making skills. Moreover, it equips students to thrive in an increasingly complex world, which could help them in decision-making in real life.

Although mathematics is important, many students still struggle to learn it. Students often lack the necessary skills to understand mathematical concepts leading to difficulties in problem-solving (Alkhaldeh & Khasawneh, 2021). They may also find it more difficult to engage with problems that require deeper reasoning.

Additionally, due to the inherent nature and characteristics of mathematics, students, for the most part, dislike this subject. More precisely, mathematics anxiety is the primary reason for this aversion.

Consequently, the study conducted by Švecová (2024) revealed that 60% of the respondents showed a moderate to high degree of mathematics anxiety. This shows that the majority of the students suffered from mathematics anxiety. This growing mathematics anxiety among students can affect them, especially those with more mathematics-related subjects. Students with high anxiety levels had low motivation and confidence in mathematics.

Mathematics anxiety involves the experience of nervousness and fear which obstructs someone's ability to process problems requiring relevant skills (Khasawneh et al., 2021). This anxiety can affect the student's willingness to engage in mathematical tasks. Also, they are under pressure to perform well and fear making mistakes.

Similarly, mathematics anxiety presents significant struggles for learning it. Many students think about mathematics tasks significantly and feel overwhelmed by how to cope with them or perform poorly. This anxiety regarding mathematical problems can limit the growth of abilities needed for completing tasks. This significant gap prevents students from building on their knowledge of mathematical concepts, problem-solving experiences, and analytical thinking abilities.

According to the study by Alcover (2024), mathematics anxiety can potentially influence students' achievement in mathematics. Students who cannot perform well in mathematics may have mathematics anxiety. Worrying may also decrease mathematics performance for highly anxious students but not for confident students. The significant impacts of mathematics anxiety are that it also influences students' performance in this

subject. This affects their ability to solve problems and further weakens their confidence, resulting in continuous poor performance in mathematics.

Mathematics anxiety negatively influences students' learning outcomes and well-being (Ersozlu, 2024). This problem is critical because it will affect students' mathematics performance and retention of knowledge and understanding. Furthermore, it can prevent students from engaging in mathematics activities, reinforcing what they have already learned while learning new things. This avoidance could result in increasing anxiety and impede their mathematical development.

Although anxiety in mathematics deeply affects students' learning, effective teaching strategies can minimize the effects of mathematics anxiety. This will result in improved mathematics performance, higher students' self-confidence, and mathematical engagement. Students who overcome mathematics anxiety have better focus and concentration while learning mathematical concepts. Likewise, using engaging activities like mathematical games strengthens the student's learning and understanding, creates a positive learning environment, and helps them perform even better than expected.

As stated by Salami and Spangenberg (2024), mathematical games are activities that engage students in enjoyable discussions while learning mathematics. These games help students learn mathematical concepts in a more active and fun way. Additionally, mathematical games can provide a fun and interactive learning experience that also serves as an additional tool for educators to stimulate students to improve their perception of mathematics through problem-solving or deepening their understanding.

In addition, mathematical games can be an opportunity to give students more interactive and relevant content for performing well in mathematics. These mathematical games help to demystify mathematics, introducing it in a fun and engaging way and helping to reduce intimidation often associated with mathematics. According to Sam-Kayode and Salman (2022), games can result in increased competence in mathematics courses. Using mathematical games as educational tools can positively affect students' performance. In other words, incorporating these games could develop students' skills and mathematics performance.

In this regard, the researcher aimed to determine the impact of mathematical games in decreasing anxiety as well as increasing the performance of the students. Despite the rising number of studies indicating that mathematical games can reduce mathematics anxiety and performance, there are limited studies that highlight the use of a variety of games, implying an area of further research. Thus, most existing studies focus on individual games.

As an instructor at Occidental Mindoro State College, the researcher has found the need to study the impact of mathematical games in alleviating mathematics anxiety. This study may help students to understand the effect of mathematical games on their anxiety and performance. Moreover, it helps educators incorporate mathematics games to attract students' interest and improve their performance. Studies mainly focus on enhancing

motivation and engagement, few focus on mathematics anxiety. This gives the foundation for this research to examine the effect of mathematical games in increasing performance and reducing anxiety in mathematics. The outcome may be used as a course plan for teacher-educators reference for the development and improvement of teaching strategies in teaching mathematics.

Research Questions

This study examined the impact of mathematical games in reducing anxiety and increasing mathematics performance among freshmen students. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the initial level of mathematics anxiety of the:
 - 1.1. control group; and
 - 1.2. experimental group?
2. What is the level of mathematics performance of the control group in Discrete Mathematics in terms of their pretest and posttest results?
3. What is the level of mathematics performance of the experimental group in Discrete Mathematics in terms of their pretest and posttest results?
4. What is the post-assessment level of mathematics anxiety of the:
 - 4.1. control group; and
 - 4.2. experimental group?
5. Is there a significant difference between the level of mathematics anxiety of the control group before and after the intervention?
6. Is there a significant difference between the level of mathematics anxiety of the experimental group before and after the intervention?
7. Is there a significant difference between the level of mathematics performance of the control group in terms of their pretest and posttest results?
8. Is there a significant difference between the level of mathematics performance of the experimental group in terms of their pretest and posttest results?
9. Is there a significant difference between the initial level of mathematics anxiety of the control and the experimental groups?
10. Is there a significant difference between the mathematics performance of the control and the experimental groups in terms of their pretest results?
11. Is there a significant difference between the mathematics performance of the control and the experimental groups in terms of their posttest results?
12. Is there a significant difference between the post-assessment level of mathematics anxiety of the control and the experimental groups?
13. Based on the findings of the study, what interventions can be recommended to help reduce student anxiety and enhance their mathematics performance?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at Occidental Mindoro State College – San Jose Campus, at Rizal Street, San Jose, Occidental Mindoro. The researcher selected forty

(40) Bachelor of Science in Information Technology freshmen enrolled in Discrete Mathematics during the Second Semester of the Academic Year 2024 – 2025 using purposive sampling method.

The researcher secured formal approval to conduct the study, beginning with the Dean of Graduate Studies at Mindoro State University, followed by the Dean of CAST at OMSC, and finally the program chair of the target program. The study involved two groups: a control group that received conventional instruction and an experimental group that engaged in mathematical games during mathematics lessons over a six-week period, from the last week of January to the first week of March 2025. Before the intervention, the researcher measured the students' initial anxiety levels and mathematics performance. Throughout the intervention, traditional teaching strategies were used in the control group, while mathematical games were applied in the experimental group. After the intervention, students' anxiety levels and mathematics performance were reassessed. The researcher used two instruments to gather the needed data.

The researcher used two instruments to gather the needed data. To assess the initial and post-assessment level of mathematics anxiety. This test consists of 15 items using 5-Likert scale developed by May (2009) – Mathematics Anxiety Scale (MASQ). Furthermore, the researcher also used a researcher-made test to measure the mathematics performance of the respondents before and after the intervention. This test consists of 60 questions, which are divided into six parts covering topics in Discrete Mathematics, specifically the Concept of Logic Circuits, Logic Gates, and the Truth Table, and Boolean Algebra. The respondents took the test for one and a half hours.

Furthermore, the study utilized descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean to measure students' anxiety and performance in mathematics. Likewise, a t-test for dependent and independent variables was utilized to assess the difference between the groups' pretest and posttest results.

RESULTS

1. Initial Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Respondents

1.1. Control Group

The control group registered an overall average score of 3.35 described as "Sometimes," based on the data shown in Table 1. The item with the highest rank (mean = 4.00), interpreted as "Often," was related to a strong fear of making mistakes in front of others. In contrast, the item with the lowest rank (mean = 2.55), described as "Sometimes," was related to students' generally feeling more comfortable during lectures or when passively receiving information.

Table 1
Perceived Initial Level of Mathematics Anxiety of Control Group

Statement	Mean	Rank	Interpretation
1. I get tense when I prepare for a mathematics test.	3.20	11	Sometimes
2. I get nervous when I have to use mathematics outside of school.	3.00	12	Sometimes
3. I worry that I will not be able to use mathematics in my future career when needed.	2.95	13.5	Sometimes
4. I worry that I will not be able to get a good grade in my mathematics course.	3.60	5	Often
5. I worry that I will not be able to do well on mathematics tests.	3.65	4	Often
6. I feel stressed when listening to mathematics instructors in class.	2.55	15	Sometimes
7. I get nervous when asking questions in class.	3.25	10	Sometimes
8. Working on mathematics homework is stressful for me.	3.45	6.5	Sometimes
9. I worry that I do not know enough mathematics to do well in future mathematics courses.	3.35	8.5	Sometimes
10. I worry that I will not be able to complete every assignment in a mathematics course.	3.45	6.5	Sometimes
11. I worry I will not be able to understand the mathematics.	3.35	8.5	Sometimes
12. I worry that I will not be able to get a high grade in my mathematics course.	3.75	2.5	Often
13. I worry that I will not be able to learn well in my mathematics course.	2.95	13.5	Sometimes
14. I get nervous when taking a mathematics test.	3.75	2.5	Often
15. I am afraid to give an incorrect answer during my mathematics class.	4.00	1	Often
Overall Mean	3.35		Sometimes

1.2. Experimental Group

The experimental group shows a similar level of Mathematics anxiety to that of control group, though a somewhat higher (overall mean = 3.40). The highest rank was item 4, interpreted as “Often,” which indicates that students had an intense fear of getting a low grade in mathematics. In contrast, the lowest rank was related to the students' anxiety, which appears to be somewhat higher, particularly in areas related to academic

performance, such as worries about test-taking and understanding mathematical concepts, with the mean of 3.00, described as “Sometimes.”

Table 2
Perceived Initial Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Experimental Group

Statement	Mean	Rank	Interpretation
1. I get tense when I prepare for a mathematics test.	3.00	14	Sometimes
2. I get nervous when I have to use mathematics outside of school.	3.25	10.5	Sometimes
3. I worry that I will not be able to use mathematics in my future career when needed.	3.00	14	Sometimes
4. I worry that I will not be able to get a good grade in my mathematics course.	4.10	1	Often
5. I worry that I will not be able to do well on mathematics tests.	4.00	2	Often
6. I feel stressed when listening to mathematics instructors in class.	3.35	8	Sometimes
7. I get nervous when asking questions in class.	3.25	10.5	Sometimes
8. Working on mathematics homework is stressful for me.	3.55	4.5	Often
9. I worry that I do not know enough mathematics to do well in future mathematics courses.	3.05	12	Sometimes
10. I worry that I will not be able to complete every assignment in a mathematics course.	3.00	14	Sometimes
11. I worry I will not be able to understand the mathematics.	3.50	6.5	Often
12. I worry that I will not be able to get a high grade in my mathematics course.	3.50	6.5	Often
13. I worry that I will not be able to learn well in my mathematics course.	3.55	4.5	Often
14. I get nervous when taking a mathematics test.	3.30	9	Sometimes
15. I am afraid to give an incorrect answer during my mathematics class.	3.60	3	Often
Overall Mean	3.40		Sometimes

2. Level of Mathematics Performance of the Control Group in Discrete Mathematics in terms of their Pretest and Posttest Results

The table below presents the control group's mathematics performance in Discrete Mathematics, highlighting the pre- and post-assessment scores. This data offers insights into respondents' progress before and after instruction, serving as a benchmark for learning outcomes without any experimental intervention.

Table 3
Comparative Analysis of the Control Group Pretest and Posttest Results in Discrete Mathematics

Scores	Pretest		Posttest		Interpretation
	f	%	f	%	
46 – 60	0	0.00	0	0.00	Excellent
31 – 45	7	35.00	15	75.00	Good
16 – 30	13	65.00	5	25.00	Fair
0 – 15	0	0.00	0	0.00	Poor
Mean Score (Pretest)			29.05	Fair	
Mean Score (Posttest)			32.80	Good	

3. Level of Mathematics Performance of the Experimental Group in Discrete Mathematics in terms of their Pretest and Posttest Results

The table below compares the experimental group's pre- and post-assessment in Discrete Mathematics. This group received a targeted intervention to enhance their understanding and engagement with mathematical concepts. The data illustrate how respondents performed before and after instruction each week, offering insight into their learning journey, growth, and the impact of the intervention.

Table 4
Comparative Analysis of the Experimental Group Pretest and Posttest Results in Discrete Mathematics

Scores	Pretest		Posttest		Interpretation
	f	%	f	%	
46 – 60	0	0.00	7	35.00	Excellent
31 – 45	9	45.00	13	65.00	Good
16 – 30	11	55.00	0	0.00	Fair
0 – 15	0	0.00	0	0.00	Poor
Mean Score (Pretest)			29.15	Fair	
Mean Score (Posttest)			43.95	Good	

4. Post-assessment Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Respondents

4.1. Control Group

The control group revealed an overall mean score of 3.35, described as “Sometimes,” during post-assessment. Moreover, the item with the highest rank (mean = 3.75), interpreted as “Often,” was “I worry that I will not be able to get a good grade in my mathematics course.” This indicates a fear of getting a low grade in mathematics courses. In contrast, the lowest rank (mean = 2.80), described as “Sometimes,” was related to relative comfort in the classroom setting.

Table 5
Perceived Post-assessment Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Control Group

Statement	Mean	Rank	Interpretation
1. I get tense when I prepare for a mathematics test.	3.25	11	Sometimes
2. I get nervous when I have to use mathematics outside of school.	3.30	8.5	Sometimes
3. I worry that I will not be able to use mathematics in my future career when needed.	3.60	3	Often
4. I worry that I will not be able to get a good grade in my mathematics course.	3.75	1	Often
5. I worry that I will not be able to do well on mathematics tests.	3.50	4.5	Often
6. I feel stressed when listening to mathematics instructors in class.	2.80	15	Sometimes
7. I get nervous when asking questions in class.	3.40	6	Sometimes
8. Working on mathematics homework is stressful for me.	3.35	7	Sometimes
9. I worry that I do not know enough mathematics to do well in future mathematics courses.	3.30	8.5	Sometimes
10. I worry that I will not be able to complete every assignment in a mathematics course.	3.20	13	Sometimes
11. I worry I will not be able to understand the mathematics.	3.25	11	Sometimes
12. I worry that I will not be able to get a high grade in my mathematics course.	3.25	11	Sometimes
13. I worry that I will not be able to learn well in my mathematics course.	3.15	14	Sometimes
14. I get nervous when taking a mathematics test.	3.50	4.5	Often
15. I am afraid to give an incorrect answer during my mathematics class.	3.65	2	Often

Overall Mean	3.35	Sometimes
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4.2. Experimental Group

The experimental group's results revealed a meaningful reduction in mathematics anxiety during the post-assessment, with an overall mean score of 2.40, which is interpreted as "Seldom." Furthermore, the item with the highest rank was students still worry about getting an incorrect answer after the intervention, with a mean score of 2.90, and interpreted as "Sometimes." On the other hand, the items with the lowest rank related to concerns were barely present after the intervention.

Table 6
Perceived Post-assessment Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Experimental Group

Statement	Mean	Rank	Interpretation
1. I get tense when I prepare for a mathematics test.	2.40	9.5	Seldom
2. I get nervous when I have to use mathematics outside of school.	2.40	9.5	Seldom
3. I worry that I will not be able to use mathematics in my future career when needed.	2.05	14.5	Seldom
4. I worry that I will not be able to get a good grade in my mathematics course.	2.40	9.5	Seldom
5. I worry that I will not be able to do well on mathematics tests.	2.40	9.5	Seldom
6. I feel stressed when listening to mathematics instructors in class.	2.10	13	Seldom
7. I get nervous when asking questions in class.	2.55	2.5	Sometimes
8. Working on mathematics homework is stressful for me.	2.30	12	Seldom
9. I worry that I do not know enough mathematics to do well in future mathematics courses.	2.45	6.5	Seldom
10. I worry that I will not be able to complete every assignment in a mathematics course.	2.45	6.5	Seldom
11. I worry I will not be able to understand the mathematics.	2.05	14.5	Seldom
12. I worry that I will not be able to get a high grade in my mathematics course.	2.50	4.5	Sometimes
13. I worry that I will not be able to learn well in my mathematics course.	2.50	4.5	Sometimes
14. I get nervous when taking a mathematics test.	2.55	2.5	Sometimes

15. I am afraid to give an incorrect answer during my mathematics class.	2.90	1	Sometimes
Overall Mean	2.40		Seldom

5. Difference Between the Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Control Group Before and After the Intervention

The results show no statistically significant difference between the students' Mathematics anxiety level in the control group (t-value = 0.0000, p = 1.0000). This means that the mathematics anxiety level before (mean = 3.35) and after using the conventional teaching strategy (mean = 3.35) remains unchanged.

Table 7
T-Test Analysis of the Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Control Group Before and After the Intervention

Mathematics Anxiety	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Before Intervention	3.35	0.65			
After Intervention	3.35	0.68	0.0000	1.0000	Not Significant

6. Difference Between the Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Experimental Group Before and After the Intervention

The table presents that the experimental group's mathematics anxiety level was significantly different during the pre- and post-intervention. It was revealed that the anxiety level during pre-intervention was not different from post-intervention (t-value = 6.4282, p-value = 0.0000). In other words, the anxiety level before the intervention was statistically significantly higher (mean = 3.50) than the anxiety level after (mean = 2.40).

Table 8
T-Test Analysis of the Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Experimental Group Before and After the Intervention

Mathematics Anxiety	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Before Intervention	3.50	0.53			
After Intervention	2.40	0.46	6.4282	0.0000	Significant

7. Difference Between the Level of Mathematics Performance of the Control Group in terms of their Pretest and Posttest Results

Table 9 shows a statistically significant difference between the control group's performance pre- and post-intervention (t-value = 4.0134, p-value = 0.0007). This shows that the control group's mathematics performance (mean = 29.05) was somewhat lower

before the intervention compared with its performance after the intervention (mean = 32.80).

Table 9
T-Test Analysis of the Level of Mathematics Performance of the Control Group in terms of their Pretest and Posttest Results

Control Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Pretest	29.05	3.94	4.0134	0.0007	Significant
Posttest	32.80	5.28			

8. Difference Between the Level of Mathematics Performance of the Experimental Group in terms of their Pretest and Posttest Results

Table 10 shows that the experimental group's mathematics performance was significantly different regarding pretest and posttest results (t-value = 11.5016, p-value = 0.0000). This suggests that the students' mathematics performance during post-intervention (mean = 43.95) was statistically higher than that during pre-intervention (mean = 29.15).

Table 10
T-Test Analysis of the Level of Mathematics Performance of the Experimental Group in terms of their Pretest and Posttest Results

Experimental Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Pretest	29.15	3.51	11.5016	0.0000	Significant
Posttest	43.95	5.68			

9. Difference Between the Initial Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Control Group and the Experimental Group

A comparison of mathematics anxiety levels of both groups before intervention. This is important as it establishes that the students in either group have relatively similar pre-intervention mathematics anxiety levels. This suggests that mathematics anxiety levels when employing conventional teaching strategies are not significantly different from those who employed mathematical games during pre-intervention (t-value = 0.8131, p-value = 0.4212).

Table 11
T-Test Analysis of the Initial Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Control and Experimental Groups

Mathematics Anxiety	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Control Group	3.35	0.65	0.8131	0.4212	Not Significant
Experimental Group	3.50	0.53			

10. Difference Between the Level of Mathematics Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups in terms of their Pretest Results

Table 12 displays the results of the comparison of the control and experimental groups' pretest results to identify their differences. It is important to determine the respondents' initial level to determine the effectiveness of the intervention. As shown in the table, the performance in mathematics of the control groups and experimental groups before the intervention, based on their pretest results (t-value = 0.0847, p-value = 0.9329), shows no differences.

Table 12
T-Test Analysis of the Level of Mathematics Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups in terms of Pretest Results

Mathematics Performance	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Control Group	29.05	3.94	0.0847	0.9329	Not Significant
Experimental Group	29.15	3.51			

11. Difference Between the Level of Mathematics Performance Posttest Results in the Control Group and the Experimental Group

The analysis of posttest scores of the control and experimental groups was also conducted to measure the impact of mathematical games on improving mathematics performance. The table shows differences in both groups' posttest scores (t-value = 6.4314, p-value = 0.0000) during the post-intervention. Furthermore, experimental group achieved an average of 43.95, indicating that their performance was greater than the mathematics performance of control group (mean = 32.80).

Table 13
T-Test Analysis of the Level of Mathematics Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups in terms of Posttest Results

Mathematics Performance	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Control Group	32.80	5.28	6.4314	0.0000	Significant
Experimental Group	43.95	5.68			

12. Difference Between the Post-Assessment Level of the Mathematics Anxiety Level of the Control and Experimental Groups

The results show a statistically significant difference in control and experimental group's mathematics anxiety after the intervention (t-value = 5.1562, p-value = 0.0000). Moreover, the results imply that control group exhibited a mean of 3.35, reflecting higher mathematics anxiety level than experimental group whose mean was 2.40 after intervention.

Table 14
T-Test Analysis of the Post-Assessment Level of Mathematics Anxiety of the Control and Experimental Groups

Mathematics Anxiety	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Control Group	3.35	0.68	3.35	0.0000	Significant
Experimental Group	2.40	0.64			

13. Proposed Intervention in Reducing Students' Mathematics Anxiety and Enhancing Mathematics Performance

A course plan has been proposed as shown visually in Table 15 based on the results of this study. The proposed course plan is composed of topics, teaching strategies, and suggested activities that comprise six weeks of teaching Discrete Mathematics.

Table 15
Proposed Course Plan for Teaching Discrete Mathematics Using Mathematical Games

Week	Learning Outcome	Topic	Teaching Strategy	Activity
1	Understand how logic gates are used to evaluate Boolean expressions to produce a result	Lesson 1: The Concept of Logic Circuits, Logic Gates, and the Truth Table a. Logic Circuits b. Types of Logic Gates c. Boolean Truth Table	Jumbo Logic Gates Puzzle Game	Objective Type Summative Assessment on the concepts of logic, logic gates, and truth tables. <i>(Activities may vary)</i>
2		d. Deriving a Boolean Expression from a Truth Table	Hunting for Boolean Pairs Games	Group presentation on solving truth tables. <i>(Activities may vary)</i>
3		e. Deriving a Boolean Expression from a Logic Circuit	Oh, My Circuit Game	Worksheet assessment on deriving a Boolean expression from a logic circuit <i>(Activities may vary)</i>

4	Apply the Boolean expression for the logic gates and combinations of logic gates.	Lesson 2: Boolean Algebra a. Boolean Algebra	New Boolean Algebra Bingo Game	Objective Type Summative Assessment on Boolean Algebra <i>(Activities may vary)</i>
5		b. Rules of Boolean Algebra c. Laws of Boolean Algebra	Equal Flip Match Game	Objective Type Summative Assessment on rules and laws of Boolean algebra. <i>(Activities may vary)</i>
6		d. Simplifying Boolean Expressions	Latching Boolean Relay Game	Group Activity on Simplifying Boolean Expressions <i>(Activities may vary)</i>

DISCUSSION

Table 1 suggests that in general respondents in the control group occasionally experience anxiety when dealing with mathematics-related situations. Although their anxiety is not consistently high, there are still instances when they feel stressed or uncomfortable with mathematics. Results imply that respondents in the control group experience varying levels of math anxiety, such as performance-related, task-related, and classroom-related anxieties. Specifically, performance-related anxieties like the one with the highest rank mentioned earlier are felt frequently. In contrast, task-related anxieties, such as worries about future use of mathematics or completing assignments, are experienced more occasionally. Classroom-related anxieties, like the one reflected with the lowest mean score, also occur from time to time. These findings indicate anxiety in mathematics is not constant but arises in specific contexts. These results were also found in the study conducted by Quintana (2024), which found that students felt further worried in mathematics compared to other subjects due to the pressure to find the correct answer and were anxious in deriving an incorrect answer resulting in getting a low grade.

Table 2 suggests that, like the control group, experimental group sometimes encounters anxiety in mathematics. Moreover, respondents were nearly evenly divided in how frequently they experience different aspects of mathematics anxiety. A significant number of items were rated as "Sometimes," indicating that many students encounter anxiety-related feelings occasionally, perhaps depending on the task or classroom

situation. At the same time, an almost equal number of items were rated as “Often,” suggesting that for some students, these feelings are more persistent and may interfere more consistently with their learning experience. This near-even split highlights the varied nature of math anxiety, meaning that for some, it arises only under pressure. In contrast, for others, it is a regular part of their academic life. These findings suggest the importance of suggesting both general classroom approaches to lower anxiety for all students and more focused support for those who experience it more strongly or frequently. In conclusion, these results point out the importance of designing an encouraging learning environment where students are confident to participate in mathematics without the fear of making mistakes. This method can help lessen performance-related anxieties and build self-confidence, as reflected in the findings of Quintana (2024), which indicated that students feel more uneasy about mathematics due to the burden of attaining the accurate answers and the fear of failing.

Table 3 shows that the control group consistently improved after the post-assessment, though these gains were moderate and remained within the Fair performance level. The most notable growth was observed where increased scores in the Good and Fair categories were reduced significantly. These trends suggest that while instruction alone contributed to performance gains, the progress was not substantial enough to elevate the overall group performance to higher levels of mastery. This consistent but modest growth underscores the need for necessary adjustments to support a more profound understanding and boost students’ achievement beyond the Fair level. This aligns with the study of Norton (2024), which found that the impact of conventional teaching strategies on students’ performance may be limited since they remain prevalent. Similarly, Dairo et al. (2024) revealed that students’ understanding and engagement during the learning process may be limited, also suggesting that combining this strategy with the other approach can balance students’ understanding and engagement, leading to an increase in their performance in mathematics. Students who were taught using conventional teaching strategies often contribute to their performance in mathematics. This approach can sometimes improve students’ ability and understanding. However, it does not facilitate diverse learning approaches, making the students passive learners and causing less encouragement during discussions (Malgapo & Ancheta, 2020).

Table 4 shows that the experimental group demonstrated substantial improvement in Discrete Mathematics. The shift from Fair level in the pretests to mostly Good and Excellent levels in the posttests highlights the effectiveness of the intervention. Beyond the numbers, the data reflects a deeper narrative that respondents not only improved in scores but also appeared to gain confidence, retain concepts, and become more actively engaged in their learning. These results suggest that intentional, focused strategies can make a meaningful difference in respondents’ mathematical development. With continued support and reflective teaching, this level of progress can be sustained and even further enhanced. An effective teaching strategy, such as mathematical games, could increase students’ performance in mathematics. According to Ompok et al. (2021), the use of mathematical games as an effective teaching tool can improve students’ performance because it develops their interest and enhances their fundamental skills in mathematics (Go et al., 2024). Through the use of mathematical games, students’ motivation, interest,

and active participation can be significantly enhanced in mathematics (Ding et al., 2018). This not only supports students' comprehension in their mathematics lessons but also contributes to their improvement in performance (Hui & Mahmud, 2023).

Table 5 suggests that while mathematics anxiety persisted, it remained at a moderate level even after the implementation of the conventional way of teaching. The overall mean in the initial assessment was the same as the post-assessment indicating moderate anxiety. Hence, there were no changes in the overall mean of the initial and post-assessment, suggesting that the anxiety of the students remained in the same range. In general, while a lower reduction of mathematics anxiety after intervention, the control group still exhibited moderate levels of mathematics anxiety, particularly concerning academic performance. The persistent anxiety around tests and grades suggests that more adjustments could be beneficial moving forward.

Experimental group marked improvement compared to the control group as shown in the results of Table 6. This suggests that the intervention positively reduced the students' anxiety. The shift from "Sometimes" to "Seldom" indicates that students experienced less anxiety after the intervention. In addition, the experimental group experienced noticeable reduction in anxiety following the intervention. The comparison with the initial assessment highlights that the intervention was effective in aiding students experience less worry about mathematics, specifically in relation to performance, understanding, and classroom interactions. However, there remain some areas (such as fear of giving incorrect answers) where anxiety persists, suggesting that further support may be necessary in these areas. These findings were observed in the study of Yu et al. (2021), which found that games are one of the most effective mediations in alleviating anxiety because it makes the learning environment more engaging and pleasant, improving their concentration in mathematics.

Table 7 revealed that conventional teaching strategy alone does not effectively decrease anxiety in mathematics. Similarly, this strategy significantly contributed to anxiety of the students in mathematics (Luttenberger et al., 2018; Zhang, 2022). However, some studies suggest that conventional teaching strategies could decrease students' anxiousness and fear toward mathematics (Doz & Doz, 2022). The need to emphasize students' mastery and foundational skills in using a conventional teaching strategy could help students build confidence gradually.

The pretest and posttest showed a difference in their mathematics anxiety level before and after using mathematical games as shown in Table 8. Mathematical games had a greater effect on reducing the students' mathematics anxiety since they promote collaboration and social interaction during the mathematics class (Dondio et al., 2022). However, this contrasts with the results of Rocha (2020), who found that the level of mathematics anxiety is not different before and after using mathematical games. The difference, therefore, may lie in the medium of games being used, in the case of this study, non-digital games.

Table 9 demonstrates an increase in performance as evidenced by their pretest and posttest results. This finding was similar to Tañola and Lomibao (2024), which found that students who were under a conventional teaching strategy frequently performed less well in mathematics lessons.

The posttest had significantly different results from the pretest as shown in Table 10. This suggests that using an effective strategy like mathematical games could increase students' performance in mathematics, since it was evident that the performance of the students had definite improvement. Students exposed to mathematical games experience an enjoyable task-solving that positively impacts their performance in mathematics (Debrenti, 2024). Utilizing teaching strategies like integrating mathematical games in class could not just increase students' engagement but also improve students' performance (Paglomutan, 2024).

Table 11 shows no significant difference between the initial level of mathematics anxiety of the control group and the experimental group. Testing the homogeneity of the students of both groups during pre-intervention was crucial in ensuring the two groups are relatively similar in the aspect being observed, in this case, the students' mathematics anxiety level. It ensures that observed anxiety levels and improvements in mathematics of the students could be attributed to the interventions rather than pre-existing factors (Pizzie & Kraemer, 2023).

Table 12 presents the comparison between the level of mathematics performance of the control and experimental groups in terms of their pretest results. It is important to determine the respondents' initial level to determine the effectiveness of the intervention. The performance in mathematics of the control groups and experimental groups before the intervention, based on their pretest results shows no differences.

The results of the posttest show that the experimental group outperformed from the control group as shown in Table 13. Using successful strategies, such as games, rises students' engagement and performance in mathematics. This implies that mathematical games effectively improve students' performance in mathematics. The findings support the conclusion of Alanazi (2020), who claimed that well-designed games have the potential to produce an improved learning setting to attain the learning targets. Conversely, Assad and Wafi (2017) showed that the mathematics performance of the students in both groups revealed no difference. This may primarily be due to the use of digital games as an alternative to non-digital games.

Table 14 revealed that the experimental group had lower anxiety level in mathematics compared to control group. This suggests that students' engagement in using mathematical games had a lower mathematics anxiety level compared to those engaged in using conventional teaching strategy. Students who actively participate in mathematical games report fewer symptoms of mathematics anxiety than inactive students (Alanazi, 2020).

Based on the results of the study, a course plan has been proposed. The students will be taught using the Jumbo Logic Gates Puzzle Game for the first week, where students gain more understanding of the concept of Logic Circuit while playing this game. Using a large grid, students will determine a certain logic symbol given its input and output. The teacher could use the proposed activity to determine the students' performance. The students will be taught using the Hunting for Boolean Pairs Games in the second week. This game could help students gain a deeper understanding of deriving Boolean expressions. Given the logic tables, the students will hunt and pair them using the Boolean Expressions. After the game, teachers will proceed to determine students' performance through activities and tests. The students will be instructed using the Oh My Circuit Game in the third week. This game provides active participation of the students to grasp more of this topic. Students will arrange and match to construct the logic circuit given the Boolean Expressions. Afterwards, teachers will provide an activity for the students. The students will be taught using the New Boolean Algebra Bingo in the fourth week. This game helps students to retain and recall the concepts of Boolean algebra. Students will create their own bingo cards using different Boolean Algebra symbols instead of using bingo numbers. Then activities will be answered by the students. The students will be instructed using the Equal Flip Match Game in the fifth week. This game helps students recognize the laws and rules that simplify Boolean Expressions. Students will match the two cards by flipping them, which are composed of a Boolean Expression and its equivalent value. After the game, students will answer the activity. The students will be taught using the Latching Boolean Relay Game in the sixth week. The students will form a circle and pass the ball to another student. When the music stops, the student who holds the ball will simplify the given Boolean Expressions. Afterwards, the student will pass the ball to another student who will continue simplifying the expression. The process continues until the expression can no longer be simplified. After the game, the students will answer the activity. Overall, this proposed course plan is comprised of various games for every lesson to make the discussion in mathematics more cooperative. Moreover, the incorporation of various mathematical games makes the lesson more interactive leading to an increase in students' performance and a reduction in their anxiety in mathematics.

Conclusions

The findings of this study lead to the following conclusions.

1. Initially, both groups experienced considerable anxiety towards mathematics.
2. The conventional approach led to consistent but moderate gains, with limited instances of high-level achievement among the students.
3. The intervention implemented in experimental group resulted in sustained improvement in mathematics performance.
4. The intervention applied effectively supported both the academic and emotional well-being of the learners.
5. The conventional teaching strategy did not reduce the students' mathematics anxiety.
6. The intervention resulted in a significant reduction of mathematics anxiety among experimental group, demonstrating its effectiveness in alleviating students' anxiety.

7. There has been some progress in learners' development, although overall improvement remains limited.
8. Each game, Jumbo Logic Gates Puzzle, Hunting for Boolean Pairs, Oh, My Circuit, New Boolean Algebra Bingo, Equal Flip Match, and Latching Boolean Relay contributed to improved student performance, highlighting the effectiveness of game-based learning in enhancing mathematical understanding.
9. The initial level of mathematics anxiety of experimental group was the same with control group, indicating that both groups were homogeneous during the pre-intervention period.
10. The initial performance levels of both groups were comparable.
11. Experimental group gained more benefits compared than those in control group.
12. In contrast to the control group, experimental group demonstrated significant reductions in mathematics anxiety as a result of the intervention.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it is generally recommended that teachers adopt a balanced and responsive instructional approach that combines conventional teaching strategies with innovative, student-centered methods to enhance learning outcomes while reducing mathematics anxiety. Creating a supportive, engaging, and emotionally responsive classroom environment through positive reinforcement, interactive activities, peer collaboration, game-based learning, and the integration of technology can help foster deeper understanding, higher-order thinking skills, and sustained academic improvement.

Teachers are also encouraged to continuously evaluate instructional effectiveness using student feedback and performance data, and to participate in professional development programs that strengthen their ability to implement anxiety-reducing and learner-centered strategies.

Furthermore, future research should expand the scope of intervention studies by involving larger and more diverse samples, ensuring comparable groups at the outset, examining specific intervention components, and conducting long-term evaluations to determine sustained effects. These efforts will help ensure that improvements in mathematics performance and reductions in anxiety can be confidently attributed to the interventions and applied effectively across different student populations.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All participants were included voluntarily. Students were not coerced into participation. Additionally, they were assured of the privilege of withdrawing at any time. The researcher ensured that students understand that involvement in the data collection is not tied to their grades. Moreover, the anonymity of the respondents and confidentiality of the responses were ensured. The names were not included in the presentation of the paper, and individual responses would never be disclosed, and only the summary of data was presented.

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